

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILIES WITH VIOLENCE IN UZBEKISTAN

A.S.Sharipova

Doctoral student of the Research Institute “Family and Women”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8306387>

Abstract. *The article deals with one of the topical issues of family psychology - theoretical aspects of the socio-psychological characteristics of families with violence in Uzbekistan*

Keywords: *family, innovations, family relationships, violence, divorce, children, coping strategies*

One of the priority areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the achievement of gender equality, as President Ruz Sh. Mirziyoyev noted in his speeches, emphasizing that solving the problem of combating domestic violence requires a comprehensive study. The National Program being developed in the Republic provides for the implementation of the main steps to achieve the de facto equality of women with men, improve their status, provides for the implementation of women's activity in all spheres of the country's economic, political and social life for 2022-2026 [1]. Currently, a number of normative-legal documents have been adopted, which are the guarantor of ensuring gender equality. Thus, in 2019, the laws “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men” [2] and “On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence” were adopted, which contribute to the achievement of equality in the society of Uzbekistan [3].

A significant step towards ensuring the safety of women and children from domestic violence was the adoption of the Law “On amendments and additions to certain legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the further improvement of the system of reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of women and children” dated 11.04.2023. , which criminalizes the commission of violent acts against women and children, and will also strengthen the position of women and children in society and will serve as a guarantor of their safety [4]

As Amnesty International Central Asia researcher Heza McGill noted, in Uzbekistan, human rights defenders have campaigned for years to provide better protection against domestic violence, and today the Republic becomes the fifth country in Eastern Europe and Central Asia to criminalize domestic violence as a separate criminal offense in accordance with the law [5].

However, despite all the measures taken over the past years, the statistics of the Republic on violence against women continues to cause concern, as evidenced by the data of the Head of the Senate Tanzila Narbayeva that in 2021-2022, law enforcement agencies received more than 72 thousand complaints of harassment and violence against girls and women. Most of which appeals (over 61 thousand, or 85%) concerned cases that occurred in families [6].

In this regard, there is a need for special scientific research on the topic of domestic violence in Uzbekistan, which until recently was practically not carried out, and this topic of violence was tabooed, and no statistics were kept.

It should be noted that scientific research in Uzbekistan was episodic, only in the last decade this problem has been given more attention.

Noteworthy is the dissertation data of Karimov H.K., who noted that one of the first who started working in this direction was Dr. psycho. Sci. Shoumarov G., who examined the ethnopsychological features of the Uzbek family, which are characterized by a rather high status of a man, his leading position in the predominant part of Uzbek families, the features of communication between the daughter-in-law and the mother-in-law, a stricter hierarchy, and other forms of expression that directly or indirectly affect the etiology and resolution of marital conflict. The author noted that 29.1% of murders in society are murders in the family, and he also made the first attempt to study the differences in the course of conflicts between Uzbek and Russian families.

At the same time, Karimov Kh.K. continued to study the topic of predictors and features of the course of marital conflicts and in his study on the example of 40 rural and 40 urban families, he found that:

- marital conflicts in the village and the city have both common and distinctive features;
- the intervention of parents in the lives of young people is one of the leading factors in the emergence of conflicts in a young family;
- in most cases, the true cause of conflicts is not always correctly recognized by spouses;
- often marital conflict is expressed in insulting the dignity of the individual and the use of physical measures in relation to the partner, mainly to the woman [7].

Of interest is the **research of Sultonova M.R.**, devoted to the study of the characteristics of the socio-psychological formations of coping strategies in women who experienced domestic violence in the Khorezm region on the example of 104 women.

In the empirical part of the study, the author used the methods of observation, interviews, document analysis, as well as the "Questionnaire for determining the level of anxiety" by Ch. D. Spielberger-Yu. L. Khanina, self-confidence test by N. Raides, R. Lazarus, as well as the methods of "Coping test" by S. Falk Mann, "Questionnaire for the study of social adaptation" by K. Rogers, R. Diamond and proved and has been proved, that the strategies used and the social and psychological adaptation are important components of the re-implementation of the social integration of women subjected to domestic violence[8].

Later, a researcher from Samarkand **Vafaeva D.B.**, studied the features of domestic violence in Uzbekistan - she conducted a sociological study in the Samarkand region on domestic violence.

The purpose of her research was to study the level of awareness of the mahalla on gender issues and issues of violence against women and girls, on the scale, types, forms and consequences of domestic violence against women in the family, on the attitude of women's organizations to this problem. A special sample of districts and mahallas provided by the Women's Committee made it possible to study three districts and 30 mahallas. In the course of the study, a survey was conducted among residents of 30 mahallas of the Urgut, Pastdargom and Nurabad districts of the Samarkand region of Uzbekistan to study their opinion on the problem. In total, during the study, interviews were held with 540 people, of which: 180 people are representatives of OSGs (citizen self-government bodies), of which 140 are women (89%) and 40 are men (21%), as well as 360 people are residents of 30 mahallas, of which 230 are women and 30 men.

One of the conclusions that should be drawn from her study is that the residents of the three districts of the Samarkand region, despite the overwhelming majority of the recognition of the

existence of conflict situations in the family, do not consider economic and sexual violence, as well as slaps, pushes, kicks violence. This shows that among the many types of violence that women experience, this type of violence is acceptable, habitual, accepted and mundane. This is due to two reasons. Firstly, this is due to the fact that in society, despite the changes that have taken place in recent years, the influence of national traditions is still great, according to which a man is the head of the family, and he treats his wife as his property. Secondly, there is a very low level of awareness of residents about the problem of violence, as well as low legal literacy. The most important conclusion of the study is the relationship between gender stereotypes of femininity among victims of violence and the nature and frequency of manifestations of family violence. Both women and men believe that women are the most victims of violence. Another, no less important conclusion of the study is that most people look at the problem of violence as a cultural and economic problem of society that they cannot control. They do not consider this problem to be a problem of the individual, his upbringing and family relations. It should be noted that representatives of the younger generation more often than representatives of older age groups are not ready to put up with manifestations of psychological, and even more so physical violence, know their rights better, are ready to change their situation, work with a psychologist, and, in particular, to parting with a partner from whom they experience violence. “At the same time, the economic dependence of a woman, giving up her life for the sake of her family, makes a woman endure violence. We can say that it is, as terrible as it sounds, getting used to violence from the victim, making it a cultural norm, is the main factor contributing to long-term violence from the spouse. Changing the cultural norm is a matter of time.” The decisive factors here may be educational programs for men and women at the stage of the marriage process, another conclusion of the study is that the respondents most of all would like to receive information about violence against women in the family from a psychologist and the majority of respondents would not like to apply for assistance to law enforcement agencies [9].

In the dissertation research by **Sultanova Amina Anvarovna** “Gender characteristics of teenage suicide”, the relationship between the presence of domestic violence and the tendency of adolescents to suicidal behavior was revealed. An unfavorable psychological atmosphere in the home, the presence of confrontation between family members, constant being in a state of PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder) may be possible causes [10].

At the present stage of development of society, a significant contribution was made by researchers **Saribaeva U. and Mustafaeva M.** The subject of the problem under study Saribaeva U. is the emergence and formation of socio-psychological characteristics of gender roles within the framework of traditional rules and social norms of society [11]. M.Mustafaeva's research is focused on the analysis and study of the features of emotional states in the parent-child dyad, in particular, the phenomenon of alexothymia, which may be the result of an unfavorable psychological climate in the family [12].

Currently, the problem of domestic violence in the family is of increasing interest to scientists in Uzbekistan. The study of the ethno-psychological characteristics of the conflicting parties in the family, the identification of psychological mechanisms for the formation of stable psychological immunity, which allows you to manage your emotions and regulate intra-family conflict, as well as the development of preventive measures in order to prevent acts of violence - areas that require further in-depth study in Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. <https://miit.uz/ru/gender/natsionalnaja-programma-povyshenija-aktivnosti-zhenschin-uzbekistana>
2. <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2019/09/05/equality/>
3. <https://lex.uz/pages/404.aspx?aspxerrorpath=/docs/4494712>
4. https://www.norma.uz/novoe_v_zakonodatelstve/za_bytovoe_nasilie_ustanavlivaetsya_administrativnaya_i_ugolovnaya_otvetstvennost
5. <https://kun.uz/ru/news/2023/04/06/v-amnesty-international-prokomentirovali-odobrennyy-senatom-uzbekistana-zakon>
6. <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2023/04/07/tanzila-narbayeva/>
7. Каримов Х.К. «Социально-психологические особенности супружеских конфликтов в узбекской семье». Автореферат дисс. канд.психол.наук, 1994 г., 20 с.
8. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/hotin-izlarga-nisbatan-z-ravonlik-hodisasiizhtimoiy-psihologik-muammo-sifatida>
9. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/domashnee-nasilie-v-sovremennom-uzbekistane-traditsionnye-i-pravovye-praktiki-preodoleniya-v-deyatelnosti-kvartalnoy-obschiny/viewer>
10. <https://interscience.uz/index.php/home/article/view/2338>
11. «Bola va zamon». Научно-популярный журнал детской и возрастной консультации, 2023; 2, с.8
12. «Bola va zamon». Научно-популярный журнал детской и возрастной консультации, 2023; 2, с.10